

APICE-Py: An Open-Source MNE-Python Pipeline for Scalable EEG Preprocessing

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Apice-Py: EEG data preprocessing pipeline

- Challenges in EEG data processing
- APICE
- Pipeline Overview
- Hands-on
- Expected Outputs, Log Files and Reports
- Customizing `apice-py`
- Good practices

Challenges in EEG data processing

Challenges in EEG data processing

Artifacts

- Environmental factors - Power line noise
- Physiological phenomena - Ocular movements, Heartbeats
- Muscle activity and movements
- Bad channels

Infants vs Adults EEG data

- recordings are typically shorter
- signals are heavily contaminated with motion artifacts
- neural signals change throughout development

Preprocessing procedures

- mostly were developed for adults
- parameters are manually set
- different analytical approaches require different preprocessing steps

APICE

Automated Pipeline for Infants Continuous EEG

Exclude outlier values to remove strong artifacts, based on the distribution of voltage values in a specific recording—either on a particular channel or from a specific individual.

Ana Fló

- Fully automated, flexible, and modular design
Suitable for a broad range of analyses
- Utilizes multiple algorithms for artifact detection and reconstruction
Reconstruct transient artifacts rather than rejecting the recording.
- Employs adaptive thresholds
Making it suitable across different age groups and experimental protocols.
- Preprocessing is applied to continuous EEG data
Preprocess the whole recording before epoching for more complex trial analysis.
- Available in MATLAB with EEGLAB integration
https://github.com/neurokidslab/eeq_preprocessing

APICE-Py

Nicolò Formento
Moletta

An Open-Source MNE-Python Pipeline for Scalable EEG Preprocessing

- Implemented in Python with MNE integration
- Open-source and freely available
<https://github.com/neurokidslab/apice-py>
- Easy customization of pipeline
- Supports parallel computation for faster processing
- Artifacts annotations
- Automatically generates reports for visualization
- Quality control metrics (PSD, artifact detection)

Pipeline Overview

Default Pipeline

Default Pipeline

1. Importing data and preparing Raw objects
2. Applying minimal bandpass filter
3. Detecting artifacts on the continuous signals
4. Correcting artifacts (if possible)
5. Redefining artifacts
6. Applying bandpass filter on the cleaned continuous signals
7. Segmentation and correcting epochs
8. Rejecting bad epochs
9. Computing event-related potentials (for ERP analysis)
10. Exporting clean continuous data, epochs, evoked responses, and reports

Importing data and preparing Raw objects

Applying minimal bandpass filter

Detecting artifacts on the continuous signals

Correcting artifacts (if possible)

Redefining artifacts

Applying bandpass filter on the cleaned continuous signals

Segmentation and correcting epochs

Rejecting bad epochs

Computing event-related potentials (for ERP analysis)

Importing Data

Data are imported and initially processed using MNE-based and customized functions:

- process eeg structure
 - accepts `fif`, `set`, `miff` formats (and other formats accepted by MNE)
- setting montage
 - standardized EEG electrode layouts
 - customized layouts
- processing annotations
- processing stim channels, events and event ids
- applying basic processing methods
 - baseline rescale
 - re-referencing

Filtering Data

Continuous data are filtered to remove common environmental factors:

- using MNE's non-causal Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter
- low pass filtering below the power line noise frequency
 - 40 Hz or 50 Hz
- high pass filtering to remove slow drifts
 - 0.1 Hz or 0.2 Hz
- only applied on the continuous data to avoid edge effect

Artifacts Detection

$$Thresh = Q_3 \pm k(Q_3 - Q_1)$$

$k = 3$ (default)

- other algorithms use z-scored per channel or on average data
- the detection algorithms do not modify the original data even if they include some transformations steps

Artifacts Detection

Bad Electrodes:

– sensitive to non working channels

- Power Spectrum
- Channel Correlation

Motion:

– resulting in high amplitude and signal variance

- Amplitude
- Temporal Variance
- Running Average

Jumps:

– when there are rapid changes and discontinuities in the signals

- Fast Change
- Short Good/Bad Segments

Artifacts Matrix

- **Bad Channel and Time (BCT):**

$$n_{epochs} \times n_{channels} \times n_{timepoints}$$

- **Bad Time (BT):** $n_{epochs} \times n_{timepoints}$
 - more than 30% of bad electrodes

- **Bad Channel (BC):** $n_{epochs} \times n_{channels}$
 - more than 30% of bad samples
 - for epochs containing 100-ms bad samples

- **Bad Epochs (BE):** $1 \times n_{epochs}$

- **Corrected Channel and Time (CCT):**

$$n_{epochs} \times n_{channels} \times n_{timepoints}$$

Artifacts Matrix

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$$n_{\text{epochs}} \times n_{\text{channels}} \times n_{\text{timepoints}}$$

Percentage of bad data across electrodes.

Artifacts Correction

Correction Algorithms:

1. Target Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

- for short and transient artifacts reconstruction

2. Spherical spline interpolation (segments):

- spatial interpolation of non working channels in a segment containing < 30% bad channels

3. Spherical spline interpolation (whole channels):

- spatial interpolation on the whole recording to minimize the use of contaminated data for reconstruction

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 - spatial interpolation on the whole recording to minimize the use of contaminated data for reconstruction

Artifacts Matrix (Reconstructed)

Corrected artifacts matrix visualization.

Percentage of bad data across electrodes.

Epochs

- Applying bandpass filter on the cleaned continuous data
- Segmenting into epochs
- Identifying bad epochs
- Applying whole epoch interpolation
- Bad epochs removal
- Evoked response computation
- Average re-referencing and baseline correction

Epochs

Rejection Criteria:

– for continuous or epochs data

- Bad Channels: > 30%
- Bad Time: 0%
- Bad Data: < 100%
- Corrected Data: > 50%

Output, Reports and Logs

Output Data:

- Cleaned continuous data
- Epochs
- ERPs

Reports:

- Individual log files
- Visualization
- Artifacts information
- Dataset Summary

```
=====
Processing date and time: 2025-05-15 16:15:21.687600
=====
IMPORTING RAW DATA
=====
Subject: data_example.set

Used Annotations descriptions: (np.str_('DIN1'), np.str_('DING'), np.str_('ET '),
np.str_('Icue'), np.str_('Ieye'), np.str_('Iout'), np.str_('ISTR'), np.str_('Tini'))
Applying baseline correction (mode: mean)

Setting-up artifacts rejection matrix. . .
Converting annotations to artifacts matrix
Effective window size : 4.096 (s)
Flotting power spectral density (dB=True).
Reading 0 ... 125000 = 0.000 ... 250.000 secs...
Filtering raw data in 1 contiguous segment
Setting up low-pass filter at 40 Hz

FIR filter parameters
-----
Designing a one-pass, zero-phase, non-causal lowpass filter:
- Windowed time-domain design (firwin) method
- Hamming window with 0.0194 passband ripple and 53 dB stopband attenuation
- Upper passband edge: 40.00 Hz
- Upper transition bandwidth: 10.00 Hz (-6 dB cutoff frequency: 45.00 Hz)
- Filter length: 165 samples (0.330 s)

Filtering raw data in 1 contiguous segment
Setting up high-pass filter at 0.2 Hz

FIR filter parameters
-----
Designing a one-pass, zero-phase, non-causal highpass filter:
- Windowed time-domain design (firwin) method
- Hamming window with 0.0194 passband ripple and 53 dB stopband attenuation
- Lower passband edge: 0.20
- Lower transition bandwidth: 0.20 Hz (-6 dB cutoff frequency: 0.10 Hz)
- Filter length: 8251 samples (16.502 s)

Applying baseline correction (mode: mean)

=====
ARTIFACTS: BAD ELECTRODES
=====
```

Log file

HTML Report

APICE-Py

Download `apice-py` at:

- github.com/neurokidslab/apice-py

Sample raw data at:

- https://github.com/neurokidslab/eeg_preprocessing/tree/main/examples/example_original/DATA/set

The screenshot displays the GitHub repository for APICE-Py. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'main' branch, '1 Branch', '0 Tags', a search bar, and buttons for 'Add file' and 'Code'. Below this is a table of repository files:

File Name	Action	Time
apice	Add files via upload	3 months ago
electrode_layout	Add files via upload	3 months ago
LICENSE	Initial commit	3 months ago
README.md	Update README.md	16 hours ago
custom_pipeline.ipynb	Add files via upload	3 months ago
main_config.py	Add files via upload	3 months ago
main_terminal.py	Add files via upload	3 months ago
requirements.txt	Add files via upload	3 months ago

The main content area shows the README for 'APICE-Py: An Open-Source MNE-Python Pipeline for Scalable EEG Preprocessing'. It includes an 'About' section, 'Releases' (no releases published), 'Packages' (no packages published), and a 'Languages' bar showing Python at 34.6% and Jupyter Notebook at 3.4%. The 'Suggested workflows' section is also visible.

APICE-Py Environment

- Install Python version ≥ 3.12
- Create a virtual environment (choose one method):
 - Using venv:

```
python -m venv apice-env  
source apice-env/bin/activate (Linux/macOS)  
or .\apice-env\Scripts\activate (Windows)
```
 - Using conda:

```
conda create -n apice-env python=3.12  
conda activate apice-env
```
- Install dependencies from requirements.txt:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

```
1 # Requires Python  $\geq 3.12$   
2  
3 jobjlib==1.4.2  
4 matplotlib==3.10.3  
5 mne==1.9.0  
6 numpy==2.3.1  
7 pandas==2.3.0  
8 prettytable==3.16.0  
9 progressbar33==2.4  
10 scipy==1.16.0  
11 tabulate==0.9.0
```

Arguments for `apice.py`

Argument	Description
<code>input_dir</code>	Input data directory
<code>output_dir</code>	Output data directory
<code>selection_method</code>	1 - Run it for all the files found and overwrite previous output files (default) 2 - Run it only for the new files 3 - Run specific files. Space key + enter key to stop the input prompt.
<code>montage</code>	Montage, information regarding the sensor locations, built-in mne montage or electrode layout file
<code>event_keys_for_segmentation</code>	Event keys for segmentation (array of event types relative to the epochs)
<code>event_time_window</code>	Event time window for segmentation (start and end time of the epochs in seconds)

Arguments for `apice-py`

Argument	Description
<code>baseline_time_window</code>	Time interval to consider as baseline when applying baseline correction of epochs, in seconds
<code>by_event_type</code>	Flag to indicate whether to process epochs by event type (default: <code>True</code>)
<code>save_preprocessed_raw</code>	Flag to save preprocessed raw data (default: <code>True</code>)
<code>save_segmented_data</code>	Flag to save segmented data (default: <code>True</code>)
<code>save_evoked_response</code>	Flag to save evoked response data (default: <code>True</code>)
<code>n_jobs</code>	Number of parallel jobs used in the computation (default: <code>-1</code> to use all the available cores)

Automated Preprocessing with the Default Pipeline

Option 1: Run from Terminal

- Open the command prompt or terminal
- Activate `apice-env`
- Navigate to the project directory
`cd /path/to/apice-py`
- Run `main_terminal.py`, using:
`python main_terminal.py`

Option 2: Run from an IDE (e.g., VSCode, PyCharm)

- Open the APICE project folder.
- Set the correct Python interpreter or environment.
- Open `main_config.py`.
- Run the script using:
 - The built-in Run button or shortcut.
 - A configured run/debug configuration.
- Use IDE tools for live debugging, breakpoints, and log viewing.

Running apice-py using main_terminal.py

```
python main_terminal.py
  --input_dir "input" /
  --output_dir "output" /
  --selection_method 1 /
  --montage "electrode_layout/montage_name.sfp" /
  --event_keys_for_segmentation Vis1, Vis2 /
  --event_time_window -1.6, 2.0 /
  --baseline_time_window -1.6, 0 /
  --by_event_type True /
  --save_preprocessed_raw True /
  --save_segmented_data True /
  --save_evoked_response True /
  --save_log True /
  --n_jobs -1
```

Running apice-py using main_config.py

```
# Directory for input data
INPUT_DIR = r"input"

# Directory for output data
OUTPUT_DIR = r"output"

# Selection method ( 1 - Run it for all the files found and overwrite previous output files (default)
# 2 - Run it only for the new files
# 3 - Run specific files. Space key + enter key to stop the input prompt.)
SELECTION_METHOD = 1

# Montage (information regarding the sensor locations, - built_in mne montage or - electrode layout file)
MONTAGE = r"electrode_layout/GSN-HydroCel-128.sfp"

# Event keys for segmentation (array of event types relative to the epochs)
EVENT_KEYS_FOR_SEGMENTATION = ['Icue', 'Ieye', 'Iout']

# Event time window for segmentation (start and end time of the epochs in seconds)
EVENT_TIME_WINDOW = [-1.600, 2.200]

# Baseline time window for segmentation (time interval to consider as baseline when applying baseline correction of epochs, in seconds)
BASELINE_TIME_WINDOW = [-1.600, 0]

# Flag to indicate whether to process data by event type
BY_EVENT_TYPE = True

# Flag to save preprocessed raw data
SAVE_PREPROCESSED_RAW = True

# Flag to save segmented data
SAVE_SEGMENTED_DATA = True

# Flag to save evoked response data
SAVE_EVOKED_RESPONSE = True

# Flag to save log files
SAVE_LOG = True

# Number of core used in the computation (-1 to use all the available, faster computation)
N_JOBS = -1
```

Expected Outputs, Log Files and Reports

Logs

- If `save_log` is `True`, log file per subject is saved at
 - `/output/reports/file_name_log.txt`.
- The log file shows
 - the preprocessing details,
 - the parameters used,
 - the artifact detection and correction steps, and
 - give an overall summary of preprocessed data.
- Necessary for reproducibility and data analysis (if the subject will be rejected or not).

Logs

```
=====  
Processing date and time: 2025-06-27 16:22:02.487102
```

```
=====  
IMPORTING RAW DATA  
=====
```

```
Subject: data_example.set
```

```
Used Annotations descriptions: [np.str_('DIN1'), np.str_('DIN6'), np.str_('ET  
(Iout'), np.str_('STRT'), np.str_('Tini')]  
Applying baseline correction (mode: mean)
```

```
Setting-up artifacts rejection matrix. . .  
Converting annotations to artifacts matrix  
Effective window size : 4.096 (s)  
Plotting power spectral density (dB=True).  
Reading 0 ... 125000 = 0.000 ... 250.000 secs...  
Filtering raw data in 1 contiguous segment  
Setting up low-pass filter at 40 Hz
```

```
FIR filter parameters  
-----
```

```
Designing a one-pass, zero-phase, non-causal lowpass filter:  
- Windowed time-domain design (firwin) method  
- Hamming window with 0.0194 passband ripple and 53 dB stopband attenuation  
- Upper passband edge: 40.00 Hz  
- Upper transition bandwidth: 10.00 Hz (-6 dB cutoff frequency: 45.00 Hz)  
- Filter length: 165 samples (0.330 s)
```

```
Filtering raw data in 1 contiguous segment  
Setting up high-pass filter at 0.1 Hz
```

```
FIR filter parameters  
-----
```

```
Designing a one-pass, zero-phase, non-causal highpass filter:  
- Windowed time-domain design (firwin) method  
- Hamming window with 0.0194 passband ripple and 53 dB stopband attenuation  
- Lower passband edge: 0.10  
- Lower transition bandwidth: 0.10 Hz (-6 dB cutoff frequency: 0.05 Hz)  
- Filter length: 16501 samples (33.002 s)
```

Reports

Table of contents

- Raw Data
- Preprocessed Raw Data
- Epochs
- Icuc
- Ieye
- Iout

Raw Data

Info

General

Filename(s)	data_example.fdt
MNE object type	RawEGLAB
Measurement date	Unknown
Participant	Unknown
Experimenter	Unknown

Acquisition

Duration	00:04:10 (HH:MM:SS)
Total number of events	666
Sampling frequency	500.00 Hz
Time points	125,001

Channels

EEG	128
Head & sensor digitization	131 points

Filters

Highpass	0.00 Hz
Lowpass	250.00 Hz

Output

- ▼ output
 - ▼ artifacts
 - 📄 data_example-epo_art.csv
 - ▼ epochs
 - ☰ data_example-epo.fif
 - ▼ erp
 - ☰ data_example-erp_lcue.fif
 - ☰ data_example-erp_leye.fif
 - ☰ data_example-erp_lout.fif
 - ▼ preprocessed_raw
 - ☰ data_example-prp.fif
 - ▼ reports
 - ☰ data_example_log.txt
 - 📄 data_example_summary_of_artifacts_detected_in_raw.csv
 - 📄 data_example_summary_of_corrected_artifacts_in_epochs.csv
 - 📄 data_example_summary_of_corrected_artifacts_in_raw.csv
 - 🔗 data_example.html

Customizing Parameters

```
apice > parameters.py > ...
1 """
2 This file contains user input or default parameters.
3 Change the parameters values if necessary.
4
5 - Parameters are initialized as classes to be inherited in specific
6 | classes rather than setting them globally.
7
8 """
9
10 # Import libraries
11 import numpy as np
12
13 Run Cell | Run Below | Debug Cell
14 # %% Parameters
15
16 """Artifacts Detection and Correction Threshold"""
17 thresh = 3
18
19 """Filters"""
20
21
22 class Filters:
23     high_pass_freq = 0.1
24     low_pass_freq = 40
25
26 class Filters_epochs:
27     high_pass_freq = 0.2
28     low_pass_freq = 40
29
30
31 """Parameters defining the overall artifacts"""
32
33
34 class Artifacts:
35     PARAMS = dict(
36         low_pass_freq=None,
37         high_pass_freq=None,
38         keep_rejected_previous=True,
39         keep_rejection_cause=False,
40         max_loop_num=None,
41         rejection_tolerance=0.
```

Artifacts Detection and Correction Algorithms

Artifacts

Initialize artifacts matrix: `raw.artifacts = Artifacts()`

Artifacts types:

```
raw.artifacts.BCT
    .BC
    .BCmanual
    .BT
    .BE
    .CCT
```

Artifacts Detection

Types	Algorithms
BadElectrodes	ChannelCorr Power ShortGoodSegments
Motion	Amplitude TimeVariance RunningAverage AmplitudeVariance ShortBadSegments ShortGoodSegments
Jump	FastChange ShortBadSegments ShortGoodSegments

Artifacts Correction

```
TargetPCA
SegmentSphericalSplineInterpolation
ChannelsSphericalSplineInterpolation
```

Customizing Pipeline

Open

https://github.com/neurokidslab/apice-py/blob/main/custom_pipeline.ipynb

Good practices

Naming Conventions for EEG Data

- File Formats for Raw Data:
 - `.set` (EEGLAB format)
 - `.mff` (EGI format)
 - `.fif` (MNE format)
- File Naming Guidelines:
 - `-raw.fif` or `-eeg.fif` – Raw, unprocessed EEG data
 - `-prp.fif` – Preprocessed EEG data
 - `-epo.fif` – Epoched EEG data
 - `-erp.fif` – Averaged EEG data
- Use clear, consistent identifiers: e.g., `sub-01_nip_task-rest_raw.fif`

Object Info

▼ General

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Participant	Unknown
Experimenter	Unknown

▼ Acquisition

Duration	00:04:10 (HH:MM:SS)
Total number of events	666
Sampling frequency	500.00 Hz
Time points	125,001

▼ Channels

EEG	128
Head & sensor digitization	131 points

▼ Filters

Highpass	0.00 Hz
Lowpass	250.00 Hz

▼ General

MNE object type	Epochs
Measurement date	Unknown
Participant	Unknown
Experimenter	Unknown

▼ Acquisition

Total number of events	157
Events counts	lcue: 53 leye: 52 lout: 52
Time range	-1.600 – 2.200 s
Baseline	off
Sampling frequency	500.00 Hz
Time points	1,901
Metadata	No metadata set

▼ Channels

EEG	128
Head & sensor digitization	131 points

▼ Filters

Highpass	0.20 Hz
Lowpass	20.00 Hz

This page says

Good EEG:

E1, E2, E3, E4, E5, E6, E7, E8, E9, E10, E11, E12, E13, E14, E15, E16, E17, E18, E19, E20, E21, E22, E23, E24, E25, E26, E27, E28, E29, E30, E31, E32, E33, E34, E35, E36, E37, E38, E39, E40, E41, E42, E43, E44, E45, E46, E47, E48, E49, E50, E51, E52, E53, E54, E55, E56, E57, E58, E59, E60, E61, E62, E63, E64, E65, E66, E67, E68, E69, E70, E71, E72, E73, E74, E75, E76, E77, E78, E79, E80, E81, E82, E83, E84, E85, E86, E87, E88, E89, E90, E91, E92, E93, E94, E95, E96, E97, E98, E99, E100, E101, E102, E103, E104, E105, E106, E107, E108, E109, E110, E111, E112, E113, E114, E115, E116, E117, E118, E119, E120, E121, E122, E123, E124, E125, E126, E127, E128

OK

Epochs Metadata

- Create a `pandas.DataFrame` with the metadata.
- Ensure rows match the number of epochs.

	WORD	Concreteness	WordFrequency	OrthographicDistance	NumberOfLetters	BigramFrequency
0	film	5.450000	3.189490	1.75	4.0	343.250
1	cent	5.900000	3.700704	1.35	4.0	546.750
2	shot	4.600000	2.858537	1.20	4.0	484.750
3	cold	3.700000	3.454540	1.15	4.0	1095.250
4	main	3.000000	3.539076	1.35	4.0	686.000
...
955	drudgery	3.473684	1.556303	2.95	8.0	486.125
956	reversal	3.700000	1.991226	2.65	8.0	859.000
957	billiard	5.500000	1.672098	2.90	8.0	528.875
958	adherent	3.450000	0.698970	2.55	8.0	615.625
959	solenoid	4.111111	0.301030	3.70	8.0	443.250

Epochs Metadata

- Attach metadata to epochs object: `epochs.metadata = metadata`
- You can now select epochs using metadata queries

```
print(epochs['WORD.str.startswith("dis")'])
```

Out:

```
<EpochsFIF | 8 events (all good), -0.1 - 0.92 s (baseline off), ~493 kB, data loaded, with metadata  
'district': 1  
'display': 1  
'disarray': 1  
'disaster': 1  
'disease': 1  
'discord': 1  
'disposal': 1  
'distance': 1>
```

```
print(epochs["Concreteness > 6 and WordFrequency < 1"])
```

Out:

```
<EpochsFIF | 4 events (all good), -0.1 - 0.92 s (baseline off), ~261 kB, data loaded, with metadata  
'lasso': 1  
'tentacle': 1  
'banjo': 1  
'corsage': 1>
```

Reports and Logging

- Log Files:
 - Automatically record processing steps and errors.
 - Save logs for reproducibility and debugging.
 - Example: `filename_log.txt`
- Individual Reports:
 - Create detailed MNE reports for individual subjects.
 - Include visualizations: raw data, artifacts, epochs, and evoked responses.
 - Example: `filename.html`
- Dataset Reports:
 - Generate summary reports for entire datasets.
 - Aggregate key information across all subjects.
 - Useful for quality control and overall inspection.

Directory Structure

```
project_folder/
├── README
├── main.py
├── electrode_layout/
│   ├── GSN-HydroCel-128.sfp
│   └── GSN-HydroCel-129.sfp
├── input/
│   ├── sub-01-raw.fif
│   └── sub-02-raw.fif
├── events/
├── output/
│   ├── artifacts/
│   │   ├── sub-01-epo_art.csv
│   │   └── sub-02-epo_art.csv
│   ├── epochs/
│   │   ├── sub-01-epo.fif
│   │   └── sub-02-epo.fif
│   ├── erp/
│   │   ├── sub-01-erp_event1.fif
│   │   ├── sub-01-erp_event2.fif
│   │   ├── sub-02-erp_event1.fif
│   │   └── sub-02-erp_event2.fif
│   ├── preprocessed_raw/
│   │   ├── sub-01-prp.fif
│   │   └── sub-02-prp.fif
│   └── reports/
│       ├── summary_of_artifacts_detected_in_raw.csv
│       ├── summary_of_corrected_artifacts_in_epochs.csv
│       ├── summary_of_corrected_artifacts_in_raw.csv
│       ├── sub-01-log.txt
│       └── sub-02-log.txt
```

NeurokidsLab

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